

CLEAN Accelerating Climate Capacity, Engagement, and Leadership Summit (ACCELS) Evaluation Report

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Executive Summary

Survey Highlights

- 89 participants registered for the meeting, 81 attended, and 22 responded to the evaluation survey. Participants were mostly in the **education** field.
- Participants were satisfied with the summit.

- Participants appreciated the **networking aspects, collaboration opportunities, and making connections** with other participants. Participants also appreciated the **working groups**, as well as **learning** about other fields and CLEAN.
- Participants found the summit useful and established connections for future work.

- Participants are likely to attend a future summit.

Key Recommendations

- Allowing more time to collaborate with others and spend more time in working groups
- Spend less time talking and presenting to attendees and focus on interactive conversations
- Having more relevant speakers that attendees can apply to their current work
- Create a space/session for educators who solely work with adults (not limited to workforce development)
- Have more focused interest groups
- Have more time to network and make connections

Project Description

The CLEAN Network is a community of practice of over 700 professionals committed to climate and energy education. Starting in 2019 and spanning multiple years, the CLEAN Leadership Board underwent a visioning and strategic planning process to reorganize the structure of CLEAN Leadership. From this, the ACCELS summit was created as a forum for groups within and beyond the Network to advance the vision of the Network.

Methodology

Study Justification and Evaluation Questions

In November 2023, the CLEAN Network hosted the second annual Accelerating Climate Capacity, Engagement, and Leadership Summit (ACCELS), which provided an opportunity for CLEAN Network members and others in climate and energy education to gather to share, learn, and explore collaborations for the next year. The meeting focused on strengthening connections around specific topics through working groups. Following the meeting, an evaluation survey was sent to attendees, which asked about their experiences. Their responses are presented in this report.

Specifically, the evaluation questions for this survey included:

- Who attended the meeting?
- How did attendees view their experience with the meeting?
- What connections were made across projects during the meeting?
- What worked well and what improvements can be made for future meetings?

Instruments

A survey was sent out electronically to all meeting attendees, using the Qualtrics survey platform. A follow-up reminder was sent following the meeting. The survey was open for several weeks after the meeting.

Procedures

The survey link was included at the end of the meeting and sent in follow-up emails. Attendees were encouraged to submit their responses through the online survey.

Participants

Respondents included 22 attendees. Not all respondents answered every question and total response counts are included for each graph. Some of this was due to using display logic to display only relevant questions (i.e. not every respondent saw every question). Please keep in mind that open-ended responses below are copied directly from the participant responses and may have spelling or grammatical errors.

Results

1-Survey Respondent Demographics

Professional Description

[How would you describe yourself professionally?]

Participants come from various fields. Most come from an educational background.

*Note: Respondents were allowed to select more than one choice, numbers shown in this graph are based on the responses given, not the number of survey respondents.

Organizational Affiliation and Description

[What is the name of the organization that you are representing/work for? Please list a short description of your work if you have no organization (for example, freelance writer, science education consultant, community action organizer, etc.)]

Participants were from various organizations. All of the participating organizations have an element of environmental conservation or education in their work.

Teaching Programs (12)

- Bard High School Early College DC
- climate education practitioner
- Freelance STEM educator
- Kentwood Public School
- MakeKnowledge
- MIT Sloan Sustainability Initiative
- National Center for Science Education

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- Ridgefield School District (Elementary / Intermediate PD TOSA)
- science education consultant
- The iCREST Foundation. The primary purpose of the iCREST Foundation is accelerating environmental education for middle and high school-aged youth..

Research Labs/Institutions (2)

- NOAA Climate Program Office
- UC ANR Environmental Stewards, Climate Stewards Initiative

Non-profit (3)

- Climate Generation
- Energy Alabama
- Renewable Energy Alaska Project

[Connection to the CLEAN Network](#)

[Are you a member of the CLEAN Network?]

2-Overall Meeting Satisfaction

[Overall Meeting Satisfaction](#)

[How satisfied were you with the meeting?]

Overall, the participants were satisfied, however they felt as if there were areas for improvement.

Utility of Content

[To what extent were the sessions and discussions during the meeting useful for your work in climate & energy education?]

Overall participants found the sessions and discussions useful in some way or another.

Other Feedback

[Please elaborate on any of your answers above:]

Respondents were asked to elaborate on their responses to the above questions. Participants enjoyed the speakers at the summit and the opportunity to be inspired and network. One thing participants thought needed improvement was having more time to spend in breakout discussions/working groups. Some participants thought that the panelists were knowledgeable but not useful or applicable to their work.

Connections/ Networking (1)

- *This was a great opportunity to be inspired, to network and become aware of other connections in the effort to increase climate education.*

Speakers (2)

- *The panelist were knowledgeable but not what I am needing/looking for right now. I wish there had been more time to connect with the working group.*
- *The panel discussion was not that useful. The presenters were all impressive but I didn't get very many practical ideas from it that I could apply to my work. The ACCEL matrix presentation was interesting and the matrix is potentially useful. I liked the idea of kicking off working groups, and I'm hopeful that the working group I joined will have a positive experience.*

Sessions (1)

- *The sessions gave very detailed insights of current issues affecting planet earth*

Projects/information presented (1)

- *My answers are solely based on the fact that I only educate present-day leaders in government, business, and civil society. This year's summit did not really include adult audiences, and the one working group with representation only touched on educating youth to engage with policymakers + workforce development. I originally planned to attend the breakout group for climate communications and journalism, since I could clearly see an adult audience for that, but unfortunately that one was no longer offered. I would love to see a space carved out for engaging with adult audiences at the next ACCELS. Thank you for all that you do!*

Breakout rooms (3)

- *The timing is always hard but know the breakout rooms (which I was most interested in) felt super rushed, but overall wonderful and thanks for putting the summit together!*
- *Longer in the breakout rooms would have been great. Too much time spent on the meditation and did not see the connection between that and the rest of the summit.*
- *Breakouts were good. Otherwise is was too much centralized presenters talking at everybody else.*

Group work time (3)

- *There seemed to be way too much time spent on presentations and so little time spent on the working groups. Yet, it was said the purpose of the meeting was for the working groups to get started... It would have been helpful to give people a chance to find 'partners' off the spreadsheet and say hi in breakout rooms perhaps I recommend using the zoom app built in timer when facilitating to hold speakers to their allotted time.*
- *We need to plan more group work time. We should perhaps have lightning rounds earlier in the program so timing can be evaluated.*
- *I wanted to spend more time in group work and less time in panels/keynotes.*

Other (3)

- *I'm a planning member.*
- *I loved how focused this year's event was*
- *I was in school and could not join the entire period.*

3-Connections

[Did you establish any connections or collaborations within the climate & energy education community during this meeting?]

Most of the people at the meeting established connections or collaborations within the climate & energy education community during this meeting

[Please describe the connections or collaborations you've established and how they will be beneficial for your work.]

People benefited from learning more about other people's work as well as tools/ideas that they can use in their own work. As well as finding others that have the same interests and creative ideas.

Learning from others (5)

- *Collaboration is so key to the work we do, and great to hear potential ideas of strategies to try*
- *I hope they will provide more connections and resources*
- *They will collaborate us in the working group to start the development of a flexible concept inventory*
- *Part of my work involves finding out what's working/can work in different parts of the ecosystem. And a bigger part of my work is trying to create a bigger momentum shift. These collaborations are vital for both.*
- *I am now connected with Rose Hendricks, who is already trained to use our tool and resides here in the DC area where I am located, so there is a potential for me to engage her on presenting it to present-day leaders here. She is interested in incorporating the tool into her work with ASTC and a project called Seeding Action, so I am trying to arrange a meeting with her and a colleague of mine who uses our tool with youth audiences.*

Similar fields/interests (4)

- *Sandra is also working on energy Ed with utilities, and looking forward to working groups*
- *Both are projects I'm greatly involved with at my organization.*
- *Found partners and set goals*
- *I'm the leader of one and am doing work in rural communities with my team.*

Continuing connections (4)

- *Just getting into the matrix. I'm sure the connections will grow very quickly!!!*
- *LinkedIn connections*

- *I joined the working group and look forward to getting started.*
- *I have reached out to Parker as a local resource to support my educators, and await a response. I hope we can collaborate on future climate education support.*

[With which people or project team(s) did you connect or plan to connect following this meeting? Please list up to ten names or project teams. - Person/Project name]

Participants connected with or plan to connect with various people/project teams including

Connection	Number of Times Mentioned
Parker Mullins (Energy Ed Working Group)	3
Concept Inventory	2
Karolyn Burns, CLEO	2
Randy Russell	2
Sandra Cipriani	2
Any Frame, Ten Strands	1
Climate & Mental Health	1
Climate Career Pathways	1
Climate Ed in Rural Communities	1
Flexible Concept Inventory	1
Interest Inventory (NCSE)	1
Rose Hendricks/TBD	1
Rural climate change education	1
Rural Communities	1
Rural Schools (Spencer)	1

4-Key Takeaways

Most Valuable Aspects

[What were the most valuable aspects of attending this meeting?]

Participants valued many different aspects of this meeting

Networking and making connections with other participants (10)

- *Sharing ideas and possible collaborations*
- *Growing the community!*
- *Networking*
- *small intimate nature of the event where we could see what each participant was working on; great opportunity for learning and networking. I think it is bringing together a lot of the people and organizations who have the most power and potential to collaborate and make real changes. I also like the shorter (half-day) online format, which made it easy to fit into my regular work week.*
- *Hearing about the working groups and connecting to the working group.*
- *Networking with potential collaborators and hearing what people are doing across the country*
- *Finding collaborators to accomplish some concrete goals*
- *Becoming aware of network connections - the ACCELS matrix. The Lightning talks were a great idea: a valuable way to get insight on a number of projects in a short space of time.*

- *finding others to work on shared projects*
- *Connecting with others! I did get a follow-up email to connect from an attendee.*

Learning about other fields and CLEAN (2)

- *Understanding the work of other organizations.*
- *Ability to share what I am doing in my school at Bard DC.*

Breakout session and group work (6)

- *Breakout session and the matrix*
- *Breakout rooms for specific topics and interactive/engaging panel*
- *Having access to the ACCEL matrix and being able to join a working group.*
- *finally connecting in the breakout rooms with work group*
- *Working Groups*
- *The group work opportunities.*

Most Important Takeaways

5-Suggestions for Improvement and Other Feedback

Future Meeting Attendance and Suggestions

[How likely are you to attend the next ACCELS?]

Most participants are likely to attend the next ACCELS.

[What suggestions do you have for making future meetings more valuable to you?]

Marketing and recruitment (1)

- *We need to really work on the value proposition for the ACCEL Summit and market it much more widely.*

Set up (4)

- *Examples of projects as they are developing and examples of successful projects in action (not just reflecting during panel)*
- *The panel discussion really didn't add much value for me. I would have preferred more time in the working groups (even maybe two separate times so people could go to more than one).*
- *Put more emphasis on the group work. Allow for breakout sessions that can rotate so you can attend more than one.*
- *I love the idea of the focused interest groups. And the mix of time in those groups and the bigger group was perfect.*

Information (2)

- *As already mentioned, a space carved out for educators who solely work with adults (and not just limited to workforce development)*
- *Perhaps more direct input / speakers who are current educators.*

Session length and time (7)

- *Potentially switching up times of meetings*
- *More time to collaborate with others, better guidance on what working groups will consist of*
- *Spend at least half of the time on interactive breakouts*
- *More time to have conversations with other attendees.*
- *see my previous comments mostly just less talking at us, and more time spent connecting would have been much more effective use of my time*
- *The agenda was very ambitious - it was a lot to accomplish in the times allotted especially when taking into account shuffling between zoom presenters*
- *Time for networking.*

Logistics (1)

- *Week ends of evening meetings would allow me to fully engage.*

Other Feedback

[Please let us know if you have any other feedback regarding this meeting:]

Most participants used this question to thank the CLEAN team for their work regarding the meeting and hope that the team will continue with the meetings. The only suggestions people had **are included below**:

Praise (2)

- *Thanks for hosting and convening*
- *Thank you for this event and to all those who contributed.*

Organization (1)

- *The panel discussion was hard to follow at times. I don't attend the CLEAN meetings so I don't have very much background in all the projects. It sounds like some great things are happening, but it was hard to keep track of who is doing what with the format of the panel discussion and being a zoom meeting.*

Length and time (1)

- *It's just too short!!!*

Other / no comment (2)

- *NA*
- *N/A*

6-Working Groups

Breakout sessions allowed participants to get to know each other and brainstorm around addressing specific challenges in the field. Breakouts each had a facilitator and 5-10 participants. The breakout rooms were organized around 6 themes:

- Rural climate change education
- Assessment of climate change knowledge in classrooms
- Justice and action around climate change
- Mental health in relation to climate change
- Energy Education
- Workforce development

These working groups will continue to meet and report out on their progress in the spring at a follow-up event.

7- Matrix Development

During the Summit, participants were asked to submit up to 5 projects they're working on to plot on a matrix and identify areas of collaboration and gaps to address. The matrix can be found at this link:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/12YC2cJhiplUUx3e1v1BgfU5bFEjbsRNMSR5S8wHVSfE/edit?usp=sharing>

The following questions were used to create the matrix and plot projects.

1. Your name
2. Please enter your organization/institution (please list a short description of your work if you do not affiliate with an organization):

The following questions relate to a single project/program/initiative you are planning for the next year. You will have the opportunity to describe up to 5 projects in the following questions.

3. Project name:
4. Project description:
5. Website:
6. Primary project type:
 - Visualizations, Models, Games, Simulations
 - Websites/Social Media
 - Online Collaborative Communities
 - Software, Apps
 - Video (films, clips, broadcast), Webcasts, Podcasts/Audio/Radio programs
 - Community Engagement
 - Lobbying & Civic Engagement
 - Citizen Science
 - Research Experiences
 - Exhibits/kiosks for museums or other public places
 - Staged/facilitated Programs (school assemblies, museum shows, etc.)
 - Place-Based Experiences, Field Trips
 - Curriculum/Lesson Plans
 - Educator/Informal Educator Professional Development
 - Non-educator Professional Development
 - Career Development

- Network Development/Community Building
7. Please briefly describe your project type if you want to add more detail:
8. Primary audience:
- Graduate Students
 - Undergraduate Students
 - College/University/Community College Faculty
 - College/University/Community College Administrators
 - Extension Agents
 - K-12 Administrators
 - K-12 Students
 - K-12 Educators (in-service)
 - K-12 Educators (pre-service)
 - Career and Technical Education Students
 - Career and Technical Education Educators
 - Informal Educators
 - Visitors to Informal Centers
 - Visitors to Cultural Centers
 - Visitors to Environmental Centers
 - Industry-specific professionals (e.g., agricultural, energy)
 - Scientists
 - Legislators/Policy Makers
 - Key Influentials (Community/business/church leaders)
 - Media Professionals (Print/Broadcast)
 - Under-served Communities
 - Indigenous Communities
 - Communities (e.g. faith groups, community groups)
 - Families
 - Youth
9. Please briefly describe your audience(s) if you want to add more detail:

Appendix

Full Survey

Thank you for participating in the Accelerating Climate Capacity, Engagement, and Leadership (ACCEL) Summit kickoff event hosted by CLEAN!

The 2023 ACCELS was intended to provide an opportunity for CLEAN Network members and others involved in climate and energy education to gather, share and learn, and, most importantly, explore collaborations for the next year. This year, the work will be accomplished in the working groups and continuing conversations, but we're still interested in your experience with the kickoff event.

Please share some feedback about this event by answering the questions below. Your responses are reported anonymously.

How satisfied were you with the event?

- Extremely dissatisfied
- Somewhat dissatisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- Somewhat satisfied
- Extremely satisfied

To what extent were the sessions and discussions during the meeting useful for your work in climate & energy education?

- Not at all useful
- Slightly useful
- Moderately useful
- Very useful
- Extremely useful

Please elaborate on any of your answers above:

What were the most valuable aspects of attending this meeting?

What suggestions do you have for making future meetings more valuable to you?

How likely are you to attend the next ACCELS?

- Very likely
 - Somewhat likely
 - Not likely
 - Unsure
-

Did you establish any connections or collaborations within the climate & energy education community during this meeting?

- No
- Maybe
- Yes

Display This Question:

*If Did you establish any connections or collaborations within the climate & energy education communi... = Yes
Or Did you establish any connections or collaborations within the climate & energy education communi... = Maybe*

With which people or project team(s) did you connect or plan to connect following this meeting? Please list up to ten names or project teams.

- Person/Project name _____

Display This Question:

*If Did you establish any connections or collaborations within the climate & energy education communi... = Yes
Or Did you establish any connections or collaborations within the climate & energy education communi... = Maybe*

Please describe the connections or collaborations you've established and how they will be beneficial for your work.

How would you describe yourself professionally? (Select all that apply.)

- Classroom K-12 teacher
- College educator at a higher education institution
- Nonformal/informal educator
- Professional development provider
- Curriculum developer
- Physical or Natural Scientist
- Social scientist
- Public Health expert
- Community organizer
- Psychologist or Therapist
- Economist
- Urban planner
- Artist
- Media specialist or Journalist
- Social media specialist
- Funder
- Not listed above (please describe) _____

What is the name of the organization that you are representing/work for? Please list a short description of your work if you have no organization (for example, freelance writer, science education consultant, community action organizer, etc.)

Please let us know if you have any other feedback regarding this meeting:

Are you a member of the CLEAN Network? If you are not and would like to become a member, please join at <https://cleanet.org/clean/community/index.html>

- No
- Maybe
- Yes